

Enhancing the Students' Learning Motivation by Using Instructional Media for Thailand's Municipal School

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ABSTRACT

In today's era, the idea of conducting student exchanges and teaching practices overseas continues to grow. In this way, the cooperating countries can share their recent innovations in the field of education. The existence of a language barrier, however, may hinder learning and teaching in the classroom. Language barrier refers to the lack of a common language that prevents people from speaking to or understanding each other. It should be overcome as the information shared between teachers and students might be misinterpreted. This research was carried out as the researcher believed that the existing language barrier could be helped by increasing students' motivation in the classroom. The aim of this study was to integrate the use of instructional media to enhance the students' learning motivation of primary school in Thailand's municipal school. This research used Classroom Action Research (CAR) design. The data was collected through the use of worksheets, still pictures, video recordings, interview guides, and field notes. The research results fulfilled the three criteria of success, namely classroom atmosphere, students' learning motivation, and the strategy's practicality. The researchers found that the use of instructional media could enhance students' learning motivation and overcome the language barriers in the classroom.

Keywords: classroom action research; instructional media; language barrier; learning motivation; primary school.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received
May 11th, 2020

Revised
December 2nd, 2020

Accepted
May 17th, 2021

How to cite

Al Mardhiyyah, S., Latief, M. A., and Masduqi, H. (2021). Enhancing the Students' Learning Motivation by Using Instructional Media for Thailand's Municipal School. *Pedagogy : Journal of English Language Teaching*, 9(1). 76-91
DOI: 10.32332/joelt.v9i1.3131.

Journal Homepage

<https://e-journal.metrouniv.ac.id/index.php/pedagogy>

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INTRODUCTION

Communication process can be interfered by barriers such as attitudinal barriers, behavioural barriers, cultural barriers, language barriers, and environment barriers (Kumbakonam, 2016). Friedman (2018) stated that language barrier refers to the lack of a common language which prevents people from speaking to or understanding each other. In classroom situations, language barrier should be overcome since the information shared between teachers and students can be misunderstood or misinterpreted. Students become uninterested on the lesson if they do not understand the language being used (Schwartz, 2014). Thus, their motivation is affected. Piaget (1954) stated that students' motivation is indicated by their active participation and engagement in the classroom. Hence, one way to overcome language barrier in a classroom is by enhancing students' learning motivation.

Various studies were carried out to investigate ways in enhancing students' motivation in a classroom. Baldwin, et al. (2017) elaborate that teachers could support students' motivation by providing an engaging classroom experience, which should be clear, interesting, and well-paced. In addition, the use of different learning methods, such as task-based language teaching method, is believed by Munirah and Muhsin (2015) to be appropriate in motivating students as it challenges students to be involved in the classroom activities. Rita (2019) argued

that the use of the right learning method, when integrated with students' characteristics and interests, can improve students' motivation to learn.

Language barriers can also impact the atmosphere in the classroom. Lee and Mak (2018) state that classroom atmosphere is an essential learning and teaching component which promotes rapport between teachers and students. Kamb (2012) argued that a positive classroom atmosphere is created through nurturing positive relationships with students, as acts of encouragement builds students' positive emotions during learning process. In line with this statement, Educanda (2018) suggests teachers facing language barriers in classrooms to reinforce positive feedback by rewarding students' active participation in the classroom. He added tips such as using simple, plain language, demonstrating instructions given, and maintaining clear voice at a slow speed.

The use of instructional media can also be implemented to overcome language barriers in the classroom. Olayinka (2016) defines instructional media as essential tools needed for teaching to promote teachers' efficiency as well as improving students' performance. It makes learning more interesting, practical, while enabling both teachers and students to participate actively and effectively. Studies also prove the use of instructional media in English as a foreign language (EFL) context to highly facilitate learning while also help drawing students' attention on the target language (Littlejohn, 2012; McDonough et al., 2013;

Tomlinson, 2012). Despite their countless benefits, however, Cakir (2015) observes that instructional media have not been utilized properly to assist language learning and that a great number of teachers resist using innovative media in English as foreign language classrooms due to limited knowledge and time.

Young learners refer to children from the age of five to ten years (Scott & Ytreberg, 1990). Arikan and Taraf (2010) state that one must consider young learners' characteristics before planning the strategy and materials used in EFL classrooms. Yetenberg (1990) characterized young learners as imaginative with very short attention span, so teachers must carefully select engaging learning activities. Phillips (1993) stressed that teachers should simplify and make learning activities interesting, motivating, as well as stimulating for young learners. Stakanova and Tolstikhina (2014) conclude that they should be motivated by the desire to succeed, explore, develop, and to improve, not by fear of failure. Then, teachers must integrate the use of games and interesting teaching strategies to balance the characteristics of young learners.

It could be said that there is little amount of research done on the strategies of using instructional media to overcome language barriers, specifically, in the case of enhancing students' motivation. This research is aimed to integrate the use of instructional media to enhance students' motivation. This study was also carried

out to provide additional information on integrating the use of instructional media by enhancing students' motivation to overcome language barriers which could be of use for English teachers who face problems similar to language barrier, students' motivation, and classroom atmosphere, especially in overcoming language barrier. As for future researchers who find this area of inquiry as an interest, this research can help provide academic resource in providing alternative source for further studies.

METHOD

Research Design

Classroom Action Research (CAR) is selected to be used as the research design of this study. Latief (2009), states that the aim of this design is also to develop innovative instructional strategy which can help enhancing students' success in learning English. The researcher believes that it is the role of English teachers to provide the appropriate learning and teaching experience to assist the students in learning English. Hence, when unexpected problems arise, it is the English teachers' responsibility to identify the classroom problems and find out the solution.

This research was conducted in one cycle which consisted of four stages as adapted from Kemmis and McTaggart's cycle (1988) cited in Latief (2012). The four stages were planning, acting, observing, and reflecting. The research started by identifying the classroom problems which

can further be improved. Then, the researcher searched for an appropriate instructional strategy to solve the problems with, and proposed the strategy in a scenario plan in the planning stage. She decided to use Total Physical Response, Audio-Lingual, and Contextual Learning and Teaching methods. Next, the researcher selected the appropriate teaching media and pedagogical instruments needed, which were flashcards, interactive videos, worksheets, as well as nursery rhymes. The criteria of success, namely friendly classroom atmosphere, students' motivation, and practicality, were also decided. Afterwards, the planned strategy is implemented in the acting stage.

The next stage, observing, is the step where the researcher, with the help of the English teacher as the observer, collect data on the implementation of the strategy to see whether it has successfully solved the classroom problem or not. It is done simultaneously with acting. On the last stage, which is reflecting, the data collected is analyzed to reflect on how much the instructional strategy has successfully solve the classroom problems. As the analyzed results of this study managed to meet all of the criteria of success within the first cycle, there was no need to conduct another cycle of Classroom Action Research.

Subjects and setting

This study took place at Municipal School 2, Thailand. The subjects of the

research were 95 students of Grade 2 students in one Municipal School 2. The classes consisted of 2/1, 2/2, and 2/3, with approximately 39-42 students in a classroom. The subjects were chosen since the researcher was responsible in teaching the students during her exchange program in Thailand, in which this phenomenon was something unusual that she believed would be beneficial for other teachers or researchers who find similar problems. As there were little to no research which discusses on strategies in enhancing students' motivation by overcoming the language barrier, the researcher believes this study could be of a worth trying innovative practice for other teachers.

Planning

The researcher developed the instructional materials needed such as lesson plans, teaching scenario, media, as well as instruments to be integrated within the classroom. The researcher created four different lesson plans (see Appendix 1) which were as accordance with the topics being taught: Colour (August 21), Numbers and Colour (August 23), Shapes (August 28), and Seasons (August 29). The teaching scenarios for the different lesson plans were also developed (see Appendix 2). The researcher selected flashcards, interactive videos, worksheets, as well as nursery rhymes as the instructional media in this strategy based on the learners' characteristics and topics being taught.

The instruments used to collect the data took form of interviews, worksheet results, still pictures, video recordings, and field notes.

In order to measure whether the classroom problems have successfully been solved, the criteria of success were also decided. In this case, the researcher aimed to create an appropriate teaching strategy to promote a friendly classroom atmosphere in order to bridge the existing language barrier. She is determined that by using instructional media integrated with the appropriate learning methods in the classroom, students would be able to experience a fun, friendly learning atmosphere that could also motivate them to maintain their interest and passion in learning and teaching activities. Hence, the first criterion of success is to have a friendly classroom atmosphere. This leads to the next criteria of success, which is to boost students' motivation, meaning that all students are actively engaged in the classroom activities.

The other criterion which was decided to be fulfilled in this research was the practicality. Latief (2012) states that strategies which involve the use of expensive materials and complicated instructions would not be of much appeal to other teachers when they were to implement in their own classes. Therefore, the researcher also developed this teaching strategy with the aim that its practicality and inexpensive aspect could be of liking to other teachers with similar problems they wish to overcome. Thus,

there are three criteria of success which are to be met by this strategy: 1) to create friendly classroom atmosphere, 2) to boost students' motivation, and 3) to be practical for other teachers.

Learning activities

This study was conducted in one cycle, consisting of four meetings which were carried out on August 21st, 23rd, 28th, and 29th. The researcher integrated several learning strategies which were chosen specifically to adjust with the learners' needs and capabilities. The first step was to display nursery rhyme videos which involved Total Physical Response. Students were to mimic the researcher's movements and sing along to the songs. The researcher also used facial expressions and move her body enthusiastically to encourage students' participation. Then, it was followed by the use of integrating instructional media such as flashcards, matching flashcards and interactive videos which were integrated with TPR, Contextual Teaching and Learning, as well as Audio-Lingual methods. Here, she made sure to use clear, simple sentences supported by gestures to help students understand. In transitions between the activities, she would ask students if what she was saying was understandable and asked students to raise their hands if they were still confused. She also asked for students' participation every now and then by engaging them to volunteer in front of the classroom.

She continued the lesson by distributing worksheets which promoted Task-Based Learning. She demonstrated in front of the class on how the worksheets were to be completed and physically model what students should do, so they knew what the researcher expected of their works. Other than giving clear, simple, precise instructions, she also made sure to not speak too fast so the students could catch up to what she was saying. When the students were doing the worksheets, the researcher walked around the class to check on their progress. When the researcher found errors, she would correct them immediately and patiently. In between the activities, the researcher implemented ice-breaking activities which consisted of fun games for students using TPR learning method. Rewards were also given at the end of the classroom to encourage positive behaviour and participation in the classroom. Throughout the implementation of this strategy, the researcher often used nonverbal communication to help students in understanding what she was trying to convey, such as using eye contact when she was trying to get their attention, thumbs up as a gesture of students doing good effort, and to give high fives when they completed the worksheets.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

In the first meeting, the researcher had to control the classroom atmosphere, which was tense as the English teacher

had to discipline them physically. To overcome this problem, the researcher decided to start the lesson by displaying a nursery rhyme video that the students were already familiar about, "One Little Finger". This was effective as the students were immediately attracted to the activity and enjoyed singing while moving along to the song. Then, she utilized flashcards to engage students with the lesson about colors. The students then played rally games to improve their memory on the names of colors in English.

The researcher then displayed an interactive video about colors. The video was paused at certain points to regain students' concentration whilst also ensuring their understanding. They searched for objects in the classroom which had the certain color asked. After that, the researcher used the colors flashcards to make a short song that all students happily chanted together. Then, they were given worksheets about colors. However, the majority of students could not write nor read in English. They did not know what to do and became noisy instead. She decided to use the attention grabber, "Hi-Hello". After that, she gave clearer instruction for students to follow. At last, the researcher reviewed the lesson by playing flashcards rally with the students and gave rewards for the most active students in the classroom.

In the second meeting, the lesson began by taking control of the classroom atmosphere, as the students were extremely noisy. The researcher displayed

a nursery rhyme video about opposites, "Open Shut Them", which the students did not know of before. However, when the researcher was using body gestures and the interesting animations in the video, the students could understand the context and quickly caught up to the song and movements. Students' comprehension of last meeting was reviewed by playing colour flashcards rally. Then, they were introduced to a game in which students must match the correct colour of the flashcard with the appropriate magnetic colours on the whiteboard. The students enjoyed this activity as they can move around, but it got a little bit disruptive as they started running towards the front of the classroom just to be chosen.

Then, she continued the lesson by counting together with the students. Worksheets were then distributed. Students were required to combine their understandings on numeracy with their knowledge about the English names of colours. In addition, some rewards were provided at the end of the class. To avoid misunderstandings, the researcher wrote the numbers on the whiteboard and matched it with the available magnetic pins and flashcards about colours on the board. Volunteers from the students stepped forward and wrote their answers. This was a really fun activity as they had the opportunity to share their ideas. Students raced in front of the whiteboard to write their answers. At last, they reviewed the numbers from 1-10.

In the third meeting, the lesson started by introducing a nursery rhyme video about opposites. The use of gestures and body language helped the students who did not know this song before. The researcher continued by playing flashcards rally about shapes. Then, a nursery rhyme video about shapes was displayed, and students were asked to sing along while answering each of the question asked. The students were highly motivated and engaged in answering the questions as they raced to put their hands up in the air. The students were then asked to come forward voluntarily and search for certain shapes around their classrooms. They loved this activity as they had the chance to move their bodies and run around the class, being active while learning. Other than that, they were also instructed to draw the shapes on the board to strengthen their memories.

The students also loved the "Guess the Drawing!" game. They took turns in drawing a certain shape on the whiteboard, and those who could answer correctly got to draw next. The lesson continued by distributing worksheets which required students to colour the correct shape using the correct colour. This activity was really enjoyable for the students as at the end of the class the researcher would display the correct answers and the students cheered in excitement when they got it right. At the end of the lesson, the researcher reviewed using flashcards, asked students to mention the shapes they have learned,

and the examples of shapes that they could find in the classroom.

On the fourth meeting, the researcher started the lesson by showing the seasons flashcards and asking students what they could see. The season flashcard each had two activities and two objects associated with seasons of the year. The students actively answered the objects they saw, such as flowers, leaves, snowman, etc. Then, they were instructed to guess which activities and things belonged to which seasons. Since they could not read the writings of the names of seasons, they had vocabulary drills by saying the seasons' names aloud. After that, the researcher displayed a video about seasons around the world. The students were focused on the video due to the interesting animations and real life situations. Then, students were encouraged to decide whether the activities and things guessed previously were correctly associated with the seasons or not. As some of the objects were incorrectly matched, the researcher helped putting the correct objects with the correct season.

Then, students were instructed to write the seasons' names in their notebooks to strengthen their spelling skills. After that, worksheets in which the students must write the name of seasons correctly were distributed. Towards the end of the class, the students were asked to come forward individually to be reviewed. They were very excited to receive high-fives for answering correctly. At last, the lesson was reviewed using

flashcards and asking students to mention the seasons they have learned and the objects and activities about seasons that they know of.

Students' motivation

Students' motivation was greatly enhanced as the researcher successfully overcame the existing language barrier which previously created a lot of classroom problems. Students were engaged in the activities through the use of instructional media. They became more active and interested to engage in the classroom activities. Not only that, but they became braver as volunteer works was not considered as a scary job anymore. Instructional media also helped students in understanding the researcher's information better, as students could visually comprehend the explanation.

Classroom atmosphere

Instructional media helped lifting the classroom atmosphere. Prior to the implementation of this strategy, students were often scared in the classroom as they were used to being given physical punishments. This made the atmosphere of the class very tense. In addition, the school hours were long, which made the students easily distracted and get bored quickly. The use of instructional media assisted the researcher in making classroom activities more fun and interesting. In addition, the games and fun learning methods combined also made the way learning and teaching is usually

conducted to be different, and this was seen as an appeal for the students as it promoted a friendlier classroom atmosphere.

Practicality

To ensure whether the strategy could be of interest to other teachers, the researcher ensured that the aspect of practicality should be fulfilled. The still pictures and video recordings indicated the practicality of this strategy. The use of flashcards was not complicated as long as students' comprehension and attention remained the focus throughout the lesson. Teachers can create their own flashcards with several little flashcards that students could mix and match as accordance to the topics being taught. These were neither expensive nor difficult to create, and the implementation of the game was fairly easy. The use of worksheets was also practical as it contained simple instructions that the researcher also explained thoroughly and clearly before distributed. Nursery rhymes are also considered as applicable as teachers only needed to display the video in front of the class and encourage students to participate by singing and moving their body parts.

The English teacher also gave several statements after the implementation of the strategy which added up to the measurements of the strategy's success. In the second question of the interview, the English teacher mentioned that this

strategy was applicable as teachers should try to use plain words and repetition. He believed the use of instructional media were also in favour of other teachers. In the sixth question, the English teacher mentioned that this strategy was practical for other teachers as it was not hard to conduct and it could help students to learn and be more attentive. In addition, he himself stated that he would like to implement a similar teaching strategy as it would help make his classroom activities more fun and clearer. Thus, these statements also added up to the teacher's judgment regarding the practicality of this strategy.

Discussion

Referring to the findings of this research, the improvements in 2nd graders of Chiang Rai Municipality School 2 students' motivation indicated satisfactory results. The different types of instructional media utilized consisted of worksheets, interactive videos, nursery rhymes and flashcards helped successfully achieving the criteria of success set in this research. Students' worksheets results indicated boosted motivation as the efforts given by students in completing the worksheet shown to be gradually completed better and better in the exercises, similar with Maulana, et al. (2019)'s study. Moreover, the use of interactive videos also increased students' interest to a great extent, as observed on the still pictures and recordings. This is in line with the studies conducted by Chen (2012), Kazanidis, et

al. (2018), and Palaiegeorgiou and Papadopoulou (2019). The researcher carried out flashcards as a part of the strategy in classrooms, which significantly stimulated students' participation. Corresponding to the results of this research, Lisa (2019) also received positive outcomes on the learners' engagement by implementing flashcards in the classroom activities.

The researcher believed classroom atmosphere which encourage students to participate more and provide learning experience which welcome students' opinions and engagement freely would be able to boost students' motivation while bridging the existing language barrier. This is in line with the study carried out by Haydn (2012), that friendly classroom atmosphere is fulfilled when students enjoy the learning process. As an addition, they were able to create their own meaning instead of just repeating what the teachers said, and hence, the knowledge is owned by the children (Pramling, et al. 2017). Similarly, Emilson and Johansson (2017) argued that students are required to participate in the classroom to have the knowledge grounded in their own bodies and feelings, hence promoting sustainability in learning.

This research was also similar with previous theories which investigated the teaching of English for young learners (TEYL). Bakhsh (2016) found the use of games in explaining vocabulary to be helpful in classes. In addition, the research findings were identical with Garton's

(2018), which discovered that young learners' participation could be improved by giving clear instructions and modelling the task's examples. The findings of this research were also aligned with a study conducted by Fransischa and Syafei (2016), in which the use of songs helped improving students' confidence to participate in the classroom as well as making the classroom atmosphere more fun and enjoyable for students. Moreover, Shin (2017) investigated similar instructional media used in this study, which were songs integrated with movements. The study resulted similarly with this research, as the use of songs and movements helped creating an exciting classroom environment which enhanced students' engagement in the activities greatly.

The other criterion to be fulfilled in this research is the practicality. Latief (2012) stated that strategies which involve the use of expensive materials and complicated instructions would not be of much appeal to other teachers. Thus, the researcher developed this teaching strategy with the hope that its practicality and inexpensive aspect could be of liking to other teachers with similar problems. The various technology used, such as the flashcards, were chosen due to its low cost making. A similar research by Yansyah (2017) considered flashcard as an appropriate media as its practical and contribute to low economical needs. Interactive videos and worksheets were also selected due to its practicality. In line

with this research, Kurniawan and Riyanto (2018) also agreed that learning video materials are worthy and practical to be used in classrooms. Thus, the researcher is determined that this strategy can assist other teachers by considering its affordable cost and it can be used accessible anywhere, meeting practicality as one of the criteria of success.

There were several highlights in the findings which were believed as significant in this study. First of all, the use of instructional media managed to create a friendly classroom atmosphere which boosted students' motivation greatly. In addition, the researcher's use of body language and gestures also helped in conveying what she was trying to say to the students. For example, she would trace the shapes she mentioned using her fingers, and encourage students to do the same. Moreover, the worksheets helped maintain students' focus and shaped up their understandings. The use of simple, brief instructions which were clear was also highly needed as students could not understand lengthy explanations. The researcher also modeled the steps in completing the worksheets before distributing them. These helped students to understand what would be expected on their worksheet performance.

Furthermore, the researcher emphasized students' participation as positive behaviour which should be rewarded. This boosted students' motivation to engage in the classroom activities. When students were seen to

make mistakes, the researcher would correct them immediately. However, she ensured that she praised their efforts in trying out with their best effort by simple actions such as giving thumbs up and high fives. This helped boosting students' self-confidence as they were not scared of failing, but rather encouraged to keep improving their work. The researcher's use of attention getters, which consisted of simple, fun chants to attain students' attention, were helpful as the researcher did not need to shout nor yell to manage the classroom. Reviewing students' understandings at the end of the class could also be done in a fun, engaging way through games such as flashcards rally. This helped reinforcing students' understanding and raising their interest to participate.

These significances created new understandings as in overcoming language barrier in the classroom, teachers need to consider many things other than just the media they wish to integrate. The use of nonverbal communication, for example, could assist them greatly in delivering information. In addition, students' motivation did not solely depend on giving physical rewards, as verbal compliments and gestures which indicated positive behaviour also boost their confidence. When the classroom situation began to overwhelm, teachers could still manage by using attention getters. Ice breaking, which help refreshing students' minds in between the activities could also still be done related to

the topics being taught. These fresh insights helped the researcher to understand ways to overcome the classroom problems found in this study.

Hence, the research question in this study, "How can instructional media be integrated in classrooms to enhance the motivation of 2nd Graders at Chiang Rai Municipality School 2?" was answered as the researcher developed several steps in integrating instructional media to enhance the 2nd graders' motivation. The above mentioned literature also provided similarities which the researcher discovered during the implementation of this strategy, which added to the answers for the research question. At last, this study was concluded as all of the targeted criteria of success had been successfully achieved and the research question was answered.

CONCLUSION

All in all, this research is concluded with the developed procedure of the strategy. The strategy integrating the use of instructional media which has enhanced the motivation of 2nd graders of Chiang Rai Municipality School 2 involved the following procedure: 1) displaying nursery rhyme videos for the first five minutes and encouraging students to sing while moving along to the songs; 2) integrating all four skills of English (speaking, listening, reading and writing) in the classroom and using pedagogical technology such as flashcards, interactive videos and

educational magnetic shapes; 3) distributing challenging but doable worksheets; 4) giving ice-breaking activities; 5) reviewing the lessons using engaging games such as flashcard rally.

Drawn from the findings of the use of instructional media in enhancing students' motivation, the strategy successfully helped students to overcome the existing language barrier, and managed to create a fun learning atmosphere in the classroom. During the four meetings of the implementation, students interacted with flashcards, nursery rhymes, interactive videos, and worksheets. After the treatment, they felt more comfortable and learned the lessons better. Previously, the language barrier, which was the students' lack of English combined with the English teacher's inability to speak in Thai, inhibited the students in learning, resulting in lack of motivation to participate.

The use of instructional media in enhancing students' motivation also improved the classroom atmosphere. Prior to the implementation of the strategy, the students were hesitant and afraid to participate in classroom activities. However, after the treatment, the students experienced a fun and enjoyable learning experience, which sparked their interests in engaging the activities. The instructional media were integrated with contextual topics the students were already familiar with. The interactive videos proved real footage interestingly which grasped the students'

attention at once. In addition, the use of flashcards was incorporated through different games which successfully raised students' motivation in participating. The worksheets also contributed significantly in reinforcing students' understandings on the topics and promoting active learning. In addition, the researcher was getting more aware of the students who needed help.

The students' participation towards the implementation of the strategy was promising. They were actively engaged and the classroom atmosphere became friendlier, hence resulting in enjoyable learning experience. This was proven by the still photos and recordings taken during the learning and teaching process, also supported by the English teacher's statements in the interview. The worksheets also indicated that students were motivated to complete each task given. This strategy was also practical to be implemented by other teachers, as reported by the English teacher. The interview also approved the effectiveness of using instructional media in classrooms to enhance students' motivation by overcoming the language barrier.

SUGGESTIONS

The researchers hope to give several suggestions for the implementation of this strategy. For English teachers, pre service teachers, and university students all around the world facing similar problems involving language barrier in the classroom and lack of motivation can

consider this strategy as a solution for those problems. However, before the treatments, it is necessary that teachers describe the name of the instructional media being used, the purposes, as well as the procedure. In addition, teachers must remember to give very clear and simple instruction to avoid any problems during the implementation of the strategy. Another critical note for future teachers as well as researchers, it is suggested that this strategy implemented more strictly and consistently in the future to see long-term effects on the students. The researcher also advises to conduct further exploration on the students' backgrounds to cover all different cognitive abilities they have.

There are several new insights elaborated in this study's discussion which could be adapted as better suggestions in investigating the use of instructional media to overcome language barriers. These insights are recommended to be investigated further by future researchers. As stated in the research background, the researcher faced several classroom problems relating to language barrier, classroom atmosphere, and students' motivation. However, there have not been much strategies developed focusing on enhancing students' motivation in order to overcome language barriers, so future researchers are suggested to investigate further on the effects and relationships of language barrier, classroom atmosphere, students' motivation, as well as the use of nonverbal

communication in overcoming language barrier, and other strategies which could be done to overcome similar problems.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The researcher wishes to thank Chiang Rai Municipality School 2, Universitas Negeri Malang, Chiang Rai Rajabhat University, and Southeast Asian Ministers of Education Organization (SEAMEO) for providing an excellent opportunity in which this research was able to be conducted.

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